
INFLUENCE OF ADVERTISING WINDOW DISPLAY STRATEGY ON PRODUCT SALES BY RETAILERS IN MAKURDI METROPOLIS OF BENUE STATE

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ABSTRACT

This study centered on the impact of advertising window display strategy on product sales by retailers in Makurdi metropolis of Benue State. The study thus focused on the nature of relationship and influence of displays on product sales. The survey research method was further adopted as the blue print for eliciting information from the respondents. Accordingly, Advertising Window Display Influence Questionnaire (AWDIQ) was used as data collection tools. The sampled population of the study was drawn from six council wards (out of 11) in Makurdi metropolis. A total of 384 respondents were statistically determined using the Taro Yamane's formula for finite population. Thus, in resolving the issue of what extent retailers are aware of advertising display strategy and use it to induce product sales in Benue State, the study found that retailers are very much aware of advertising display strategy. Also, retailers use advertising window display strategy very often to induce product sales. The study however found that there is an average sales rate as a result of advertising window display strategy. On how retailers use display strategy of advertising to influence product sales in Benue State, the study found that; by making the customer to look twice, by luring the customer into the shop, by giving the customer the opportunity to see all the shop stock and by making the customer to purchase product from the shop. The study also found that the influence nature of advertising window display strategy on product sales is highly favourable. Testes hypothesis also show that there was significant influence in the use of advertising display strategy and product sales by retailers in Benue state. The third phase of the study sought the nature of relationship between advertising display strategy and product sales by retailers in Benue state. The study found that the nature of relationship is very positive. Tested hypothesis also showed that there was significant positive relationship in the use of display strategy by retailers and product sales in Benue state. The last phase of the study sought possible way that could help improve advertising display strategy by retailers in Benue state. The study found that display could be improved upon by; helping customers find locations within the store, enhancing the store ambiance and environment, improving marketing and merchandising effectiveness and by promoting new products, product lines, or product categories.

Keywords: Advertising Window; Display Strategy; Product Sales; Retailers; Population

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Advertising window display is a campaign tactic developed to communicate ideas about products and services to potential consumers in the hopes of convincing them to buy those products and services. A walk-through various retailers' shops and supermarkets in Makurdi Metropolis of Benue State will show how various shop owners and business people display their products to persuade customers and even passer by. Most of the shops owners even went as far as displaying dummies of products they are selling while others display the real product. The probable intent is to woo customer or clients in other to sell their product. The implication of product display may also be that, the more retailers engaged in display of their products, the more likely will they generate sales.

One of the key instruments of many retailers' communication strategy is their store window displays (Gentry 2008). Researches on window displays and consumer shopping decisions by Castaneda (1996) and Fletcher (1987) found that consumers are very likely to attend to and acquire information from window displays. Corroborating, Sen, Lauren and Chandran (2002) assert that window displays are akin to advertising in helping create and maintain an overall image of the retailer in consumers' minds. However, by virtue of their location at the purchase site, windows, like other sales promotions, can also directly induce consumers into the store to make specific purchases.

Sen, Lauren, and Chandran (2002) assert that advertising as an integral part for both social and economic system has grown over the years to tremendously assume proportions not only as a business activity, but also as a social phenomenon. That is to say that advertising is ubiquitous and every person who resides and works in this modern world is under the influence of advertising. Apart from the advertisement watched on television, heard on the radio and read from papers, there are many other advertisements seen when walking around the streets. These include the display of goods at shops, posters, bill boards, cultural displays and so on. This tells the unavoidability of advertising in this present world. To support this view, Dyer (2002, p. 1) writes:

Anyone living and working in any modern society today is under the influence of advertising. Every day and for most of our lives we see and hear many advertisements. Even if you don't read a newspaper or watch television and walk around the street with your eyes down you will find it impossible to avoid some form of publicity, even if it is only a trade display at a local store, uninvited handbills pushed through the letter box or cards displayed in the window for the corner news agent.

In this light, the urge to advertise according to Klepper (1999) seems to be a part of human nature evidenced since ancient times. Hence, advertising creates and promotes general awareness among consumers, for the availability of product alternatives. By so doing, it promotes free and rational consumer choice. When goods and services are made known to people through advertising, their market appeal is broadened and this facilitates sales growth. High profits reflect larger sales volume of resulting from successful advert sign rather than the exercise of market power to charge high monopoly price (Daniel 1990). Advertising therefore, is not merely a means of registering a brand names, but means of competitive persuasion as well. Since consumers do not accept any product without strong resentment, it implies that it is only the successful advert sign of good quality products that lead to brisk sales of the product as a result of positive reaction by the consumers.

Gentry (2008) posits that display as one of early Nigerian method of advertising attracts a lots of sales especially when the product for sale is well displayed. Edible things such as fried

chicken, ground fruits, orange, banana, when beautifully displayed become attractive and can make someone buy it even when he never thought of doing so. Although, the methods of display in Nigeria were unsophisticated and also got to a limited audience, sellers of goods and services found them even useful in making the availability of their goods and services known; buyers and users used them to know where the products and services they wanted actually existed.

It is in this light that Ozoh (1998, p. 48) writes, the majority of ads carried in newspapers are usually display ads. It is important to note that the emergence of modern advertising has not relegated the traditional display method of advertising to the background. It is still widely practiced in Nigeria today. This however underscores the importance of display strategy of advert sign in the world of business. Corroborating, Malickson and Nason (2007) opined that the influence of displays, particularly relative to other marketing actions, is likely to depend on various characteristics of the consumer, the product category, the retail context, and the shopping task. However, an understanding of this potentially complex relationship between window displays and shopping decisions is predicated on evidence of its existence. In attempting to shed light on the existence and nature of this relationship, this research seeks to examine the role of window displays retailers in consumer shopping decisions.

2.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Introduction

This chapter deals with the review of relevant literature to the study. The chapter is divided into review of concepts, review of related literature, review of empirical studies, theoretical framework and the chapter summary as they relate to one another.

2.2 Review of Concepts

The section put into perspective the concepts of Retailer, Window Display Strategy and Advertising.

2.2.1 Retailer

The term retail according to the American Heritage New Dictionary of Cultural Literacy (2005) is a term describing businesses that sell goods directly to individuals. Corroborating this definition, Mandell and Rosenberg (2001) define a retailer as one who sells primarily to the consumers. The items are purchase from the manufacturer or wholesaler and sold to the end user at a marked up price.

Waters (2012) defines a retailer as a person who purchases a variety of goods in small quantities from different wholesalers and sells them to the ultimate consumer; he is the last link in the chain of distribution from the producer to the consumer. He provides ready stock goods and as such he sells the quantity of goods desired by the customers. He keeps a large variety of goods produced by different producers and thereby ensures a wide variety of choice to the customers. He relieves the consumers of maintaining large quantity of goods for future period because he himself holds large stock of goods. He develops personal relationship with the customers by giving them credit.

According to Krafft, and Mantrala (2006, p. 54) retailing is the process of selling consumer goods and/or services to customers through multiple channels of distribution to earn a profit. Demand is created through diverse target markets and promotional tactics, satisfying consumers' wants and needs through a lean supply chain. The authors added that retailing includes subordinated services, such as delivery. The term retailer is also applied where a

service provider services the needs of a large number of individuals, such as for the public. Shops may be on residential streets, streets with few or no houses, or in a shopping mall. Shopping streets may be for pedestrians only. Sometimes a shopping street has a partial or full roof to protect customers from precipitation.

From the definitions provided, retailer in the context of this study covers the sale of goods or commodities in small quantities directly to ultimate consumers. It is a business or person that sells goods to the consumer, as opposed to a wholesaler or supplier, who normally sell their goods to another business.

2.2.2 Window Display

Display strategy is the display of goods in a window designed to attract customers; it is an arrangement of items in a shop window. It is a window of a store facing onto the street; used to display merchandise for sale in the store (Park, Iyer, and Smith, 1989).

Hadley (2014) asserts that a display window (also shop window or store window), is a window in a shop displaying items for sale or otherwise designed to attract customers to the store. Usually, the term refers to larger windows in the front facade of the shop. The author adds that, displaying merchandise in a store window is known as window dressing, which is also used to describe the items displayed themselves.

Writing on window display, Faillo (2013, p. 118) asserts that:

As marketers, we all want people to know about our brand and what we do. Once people are aware of our brand, we also want them to do business with us. Display advertising can fast track brand awareness quickly, delivering your brand's imagery and messaging to your desired audience.

Retailers use display strategy to show merchandise, provide customers with product information, get customers to stop and shop at the store, reinforce print and other forms of advertising, and promote the store's image. Farese, Kimbrell, and Woloszyk (1997, pp. 284-285) pointed out that window display, when available on building's exterior, are especially useful for visual merchandising. They classify five interior displays as; open displays, closed displays, point of purchase displays, architectural displays and store decorations. Open display strategy allow customers to handle and examine merchandise, whereas closed displays only allow customers to see but not handle merchandise for security reasons. Point-of purchase displays are designed mainly to promote impulse purchases. Architectural displays involve model rooms that allow customers to see how merchandise might look in their homes. Store decorations are displays that coincide with specific seasons or holidays such as display of Christmas trees and other items to invoke the spirit of Christmas.

Owing from the conceptualization above, one can say that product display does not imply total showcasing or exposition of products, but a strategic display of essential products which have a potential effect of leading to the purchase of other products that go with it.

2.2.3 Advertising

Kotler (1988) sees advertising as one of the four major tools (among sales promotion, personal selling and direct mail) companies use to direct persuasive communications to target buyers and public. He adds that advertising consists of non-personal forms of communication conducted through paid media under clear sponsorship. According to him, the purpose of

advertising is to enhance potential buyers' responses to the organization and its offering, emphasizing that "it seeks to do this providing information, by channeling desire, and by supplying reasons for preferring a particular organization's offer.

The Advertising Practitioners Council of Nigeria, APCON (1988) defines advertising as a form of communication through media about products, services, or ideas, paid for by an identified sponsor. Corroborating, Kotler and Keller (2008) define advertising as any paid form of non-personal presentation and promotion of ideas, goods, or services by an identified sponsor. Advertisers include not only business firms but also charitable, nonprofit, and government agencies. Similarly, Morden (1991) earlier noted that advertising is used to establish a basic awareness of the product or service in the mind of the potential customer and to build up knowledge about it.

Sambe (2005) defines advertising as any paid form of non-personal presentation and promotion of idea, goods or services by an identified sponsor. Bovee and Arens (1982) define advertising as non-personal communication of information usually paid for and usually identified with sponsors through the various media.

The foregoing definitions presuppose that advertising is a dissemination of information about who has paid for such communication and who has chosen the appropriate medium he feels will effectively deliver his message to the target audience. It means drawing attention to something, notifying or informing somebody of something.

2.3 Influence of Advertising on the Society

Advertising is a form of communication intended to persuade an audience (viewers, readers or listeners) to purchase or take some action upon products, ideals, or services. It includes the name of a product or service and how that product or service could benefit the consumer, to persuade a target market to purchase or to consume that particular brand. These brands are usually paid for or identified through sponsors and viewed via various media (Sindhya, 2013, p. 2).

Advertising is a campaign developed to communicate ideas about products and services to potential consumers in the hopes of convincing them to buy those products and services. The campaign when built in a rational and intelligent manner will reflect other business considerations (overall budget, brand recognition efforts) and objectives (public image enhancement, market share growth) as well. Accordingly, Hiam and Charles (1992) pointed out that most advertising strategies focus on achieving three general goals;

- 1) Promote awareness of a business and its product or services;
- 2) Stimulate sales directly and attract competitors' customers; and
- 3) Establish or modify a business' image.

In other words, advertising seeks to inform, persuade, and remind the consumer. With these aims in mind, most businesses follow a general process which ties advertising into the other promotional efforts and overall marketing objectives of the business. According to Sawyer (2004, p.54), the objective of advertising is to increase your profit by increasing your sales. Advertising aims to:

- Make your business and product name familiar to the public
- Create goodwill and build a favourable image
- Educate and inform the public

- Offer specific products or services
- Attract customers to find out more about your product or service

By implication, advertising has become one of the crucial factors that determines the style and functioning of one's life in different contexts in the society. Corroborating, Belch (2001) pointed out that some subtle changes in the practice of advertising have been reshaping the society people live in. The force of advertising reaches out and touches everyone living and working in the modern world today. In a similar vein, Lee and Johnson (1999) assert that advertising is claimed by its practitioners to be largely responsible for the good things in life and is criticized by its opponents as the cause of unpleasant things. Assorted techniques are enforced for persuading consumers that they want the product which is being advertised. These techniques usually give attention to the benefits that would be brought to the consumers rather than focusing on the actual products. For instance, an automobile advertisement advertising the mechanical attributes of a vehicle, most likely concentrates the exhilaration, reputation and social progression it may bring to the buyer.

The impact of advertising on our society is in a jumble form, depending on the functions and implementations of numerous campaigns. Our society and the marketing of products depend very badly upon advertising. The companies have become much dependent of advertising that even its negative impacts can never outweigh the many positive social and economic effects. According to Jack (2008), the most important element of advertising is not information but suggestion more or less making use of associations, emotions (appeal to emotion) and drives dormant in the subconscious of people, such as sex drive, herd instinct; of desires, such as happiness, health, fitness, appearance, self-esteem, reputation, belonging, social status, identity, adventure, distraction, reward; of fears (appeal to fear), such as illness, weaknesses, loneliness, need, uncertainty, security or of prejudices, learned opinions and comforts. All human needs, relationships, and fears – the deepest recesses of the human psyche – become mere means for the expansion of the commodity universe under the force of modern marketing.

Summarily therefore, Berkers (2009) writing on the influence of advertising states that, an obvious reason for advertising is simply informing people of the existence of products they might be interested in buying. No one will buy something that they don't know exists. When more people know about a product, more of it will be sold. Corroborating, Boykin(2009) asserts that the primary function of advertising is to persuade people to buy something. Consequently, understanding how advertising influences people is an exercise in understanding how persuasion techniques are used in advertising to trigger buying decisions. Persuasion techniques can be either rational, irrational or a combination of both. Boykin (2009) further explained thus:

Informational Advertising: Rational techniques are used in so-called informational advertising because information is used to help people make informed buying decisions. A defining characteristic of informational advertising is that it is product centered as opposed to user centered advertising. Informational advertising provides factual and relevant information about a product or service. This information is provided under the presumption of knowing what is important to prospective buyers who can accept the information as verifiable. Informational advertising might focus on product features and benefits, product performance, comparisons with competitive products or other fact-based arguments that lead consumers to logical and informed decisions.

Transformational Advertising: Irrational techniques are used in so-called transformational or experiential advertising. Unlike informational advertising that is product-centered advertising; transformational advertising is user-centered advertising. This form of advertising is based on the promise of a singularly unique user experience that the product or service delivers to users, which cannot be replicated by competing brands. Transformational advertising promises user experiences that generally improve one's quality of life, such as more fun, more glamorous, more exciting, warmer, richer and more satisfying. Transformational advertising attempts to link the experience communicated in the advertising with the experience of brand usage such that the experience and the brand are interconnected.

Irrational Techniques: Irrational techniques in advertising appeal to people's emotions. Emotional appeals attempt to substitute intuitive judgment for logic in the purchase decision-making process. This intuitive approach to decision-making is dependent on how people feel about the brand and the company behind the brand. This is a matter of trust. People who hold advertisers in high regard in terms of trust are more inclined to make decisions based on judgment rather than logic. Emotional appeals obviously won't work when people don't trust or don't know the advertiser. Therefore, before you can hope to have success with emotional appeals, you must earn the trust of your target audience. You have a brand when you have the trust of your audience. Moreover, your brand can command premium prices, because people readily pay higher prices for brands they trust.

2.4 Importance of Advertising window Display on Product Sale

One of the key tools of many retailers' communication strategy is their store window displays. Display is a form of communication designed to persuade potential customers to choose your product or service at the store or supermarket. Successful display involves making your products or services known by displaying them at the front of the shop or window of your shop so that the customers will purchase them. According to Hendel and Nevo (2006), the main objectives of display strategy of advertising whether traditional or modern is to enhance sales. Products are displayed or exhibited by retailers to attract prospective buyer's attention which eventually result in the purchase of such products.

The implication of the assertion above is that a customer is easily enticed and is likely to pay attention to product displayed. Recent surveys suggest that consumers are very likely to attend to and acquire information from window displays (Castaneda, 1996). Similarly, a renewed faith among retailers in the ability of window displays to capture consumers' attention and draw them into a store has generated recent interest in this communication tool after years of neglect. This paucity is underscored by the possibility that window displays, in their effect on retailer-related cognitions and decisions, can function both as advertising and sales promotion (Horvitz, 1998). Window displays are akin to advertising in helping create and maintain an overall image of the retailer in consumers' minds (Park, Jaworski and

Macinnis, 1986). However, by virtue of their location at the purchase site, windows, like other sales promotions, can also directly induce consumers into the store to make specific purchases.

Products are advertised chiefly to accord them wide publicity and eventually selling them. The efforts of the advertisers need to be complemented and the only way of doing this is by ensuring that the products advertised are readily available in the market place and also being well displayed. This, Doughudje (1985) writing on the importance of display pointed out that:

We don't want to advertise when dealers and distributors are not stocking your brand. We don't want to advertise when your brand is not on display in the hawker's tray or in the market mammy's shop. It is your task to see to the availability of the product in the market place. And it is only by doing that successfully that you can complement our efforts. It is no use singing the praise of your brand when the consumer cannot find it to buy. So help by ensuring that your brand is stocked and well displayed by distributors and traders.

The influence of window displays, particularly relative to other marketing actions, is likely to depend on various characteristics of the consumer, the product category, the retail context, and the shopping task. However, an understanding of this potentially complex relationship between window displays and shopping decisions is predicated on evidence of its existence. Displays are very essential for retailers in their quest to attract attention and sale products. Kaufman (1987) asserts that displays at the point of purchase (POP) are a widely used as retailing device for drawing customer's attention. Display strategy for advertising does not imply total exposition but a strategic showcasing for essential products which have the potential effect for what can be called a domino sale. This means displaying few of the original products where applicable and/or sample or dummy of the product. For instance, the display of engine oil could lead to the sale of oil filter but while engine oil can be easily displayed, oil filter may not. Hence;

Point of purchase display offer advertisers the opportunity to present their products to the consumers at the time he or she is about to make purchase. The free-standing coke display and merchandiser not only helps stimulate sale of the product, but other products that go with coke (Kaufman, 1987 p. 302).

Display strategy of advertising therefore enables the buyers to make purchase decision in the shop. It enables the customers to make a wide range of a choice on seeing a variety of products on display. Take for instance, a display of variety of treated and untreated engine oil, alongside with oil treatments makes the buyers decide whether to buy treated engine oil and leave out oil treatment or to buy untreated engine oil with the oil treatment. Again, the sight of beautiful display could make a buyer decide to buy a new brand of engine oil due to the beautiful packaging, and leave out the already existing one he used to buy. Supporting this, Boone and Kurtz (2004, p. 553) assert that this method of sales promotion capitalizes on the fact that buyers make many purchase decisions within the store, so it encourages retailers to improve on site-merchandising that directly benefit the retailer by creating special displays designed to stimulate sales of the item being promoted.

It is also pertinent to say that through the display of products by retailers, both the current and potential customers get to know about the availability of new product a shopping mall. The customers get to see the product, feel it and even taste it. The customers get more informed

about the new product through face-to-face contact with the seller. To support this position, Dwyer and Tanner (2002, p. 347) affirmed that because buyers depend on displays to see new products and keep abreast of the latest information, display and exhibition are important to business marketers. For instance, a buyer of 'Abro' transmitter or 'Magic-dash board polish' for cars will get to know about the existence of 'Formula I brand' through display at the selling center. It is when the customer sees the product that he will ask questions and the seller will inform and educate him on how to use it. Display in this way creates dialogue and strengthens the relationship between the buyer and the seller.

Product display is therefore an important way of getting new customers. Writing on product display, Terpstra and Sarathy (1994) noted that even though the packaging of a product plays a role in persuading the consumer, displaying the products give the buyer the chance to have a first-hand overview of the product.

It is also pertinent to observe at this point that the kind of display a product gets in a retail outlet depends on the physical facilities of space, shelves, and lighting. The more products are displayed, the more the beauty of the packaged products is projected. This in turn draws the attention of the passersby. The magnitude of the display all depends on the size of the shop and capital. Some shops are small with little space, no electric lighting, one door and one window, a few shelves, and one or two tables. In larger shops like supermarkets, products are largely display both inwardly and outwardly. In fact, the beauty of display is glaringly seen in large departmental stores such as Nobis Supermarket, Togos Supermarket, GO Brothers and the like in Makurdi Town, where products are exquisitely displayed. A customer who enters there with a bag filled with money might end up exhausting it. This is as a result of power of attraction embedded in beautifully displayed packaged products. It is due to the important of display that representatives of the manufacturers arrange the display themselves. Product display is frequently all that a manufacture can expect from retailers. This tells why a company like Coca-Cola for instance, will go about giving out their refrigerators to retailers on condition that only Coca-Cola product will be displayed in it.

Thus, companies increasingly depend on sales promotion in order to among other things; get retailers to allocate some of their precious shelf space to new brands of display. The competition for shelf space for new products goes a long way in simplifying the decision-making for buyers. This is due to the fact that they (buyers) will feel that the products on display are better and more effective than the ones not displayed, the buyers therefore go for the products on display in order to have real value for their money. This according to George and Michael (2001) means buying a brand that is on special or being displayed can simplify the decision-making process and solve the problem of over choice.

2.5 Review of Empirical Studies

Several researches on advertising and display have been analyzed to give empirical touch to this study. Foremost is the study by Ayanwale, Alimi and Ayanbimipe (2005) on the Influence of Advertising on Consumer Brand Preference. The purpose of this study was to examine activities of Cadbury Nigeria PLC with respect to branding and advertising of Bournvita which is the flagship of its products. Specifically, the research examined the influence of advertising on consumer buying behaviours preferences. The study employed survey method and 350 (three hundred and fifty) copies of questionnaire were administered on the members of the public through trained personnel in three major cities namely: Lagos, Ibadan and Ile-Ife at 150,100, and 100 copies, respectively. The respondents were selected randomly at each of the locations while the distribution was aimed at reflecting the population of each of these cities.

The obtained data from the survey supported the motion that brand preference exists in the food drink industry and that advertising efforts affect product preferences. Of more than 12 different food drinks brands which featured in this study, Bournvita topped the brand preference table both in the food drink industry in general and in Cadbury's food drink brands in particular implying that it still remains the favourite food drink consumers enjoys and have undisputed loyalty among the largest percentage of the respondents. According to the respondents, advertising and quality are the major factors responsible for the success of Bournvita. Very few subjects cited other reasons such as price, packaging and availability for their choice of the brand.

The implication of the findings of the study by Ayanwale, Alimi and Ayanbimipe (2005) to this current study is that advertising could determine product preference of customers. Hence, as product are been displayed, they are capable of inducing sales. However, that study was on the influence of advertising on consumer brand preference while this study investigates the relationship between display strategy of advertising and product sales by retailers.

Kanchori (2014) carried out a study on the influence of digital signage usage on product sale among leading supermarkets in Kenya. The target populations of the study were; management and sales representatives/merchandisers who work for Uchumi, Tuskys and Nakumatt supermarkets. The study adopted a descriptive research design and sampled 485 respondents for the study.

In order to determine the effect of digital signage on product sales in the supermarkets, the study found that the aggregate mean score of product sales measures were regressed against the mean score of measures of digital signage. The regression results also show that at individual level, there was a statistically significant positive linear relationship between product sales in the supermarkets and digital signage usage. The regression results also shows that product sales in the supermarkets can be explained by digital signage usage and the relationship between the digital signage usage and product sales followed a simple regression model of the nature. In all, the study found that digital displays provide essential information on products available in the store.

The relevance of the study by Kanchori (2014) to this study is that the study was centered of advertising display and product sales in supermarkets. However, while the study was on digital display and carried out in Kenya, this study is on window display at point of purchase and done in Nigeria.

In another study, Chiliya, Herbst and Roberts-Lombard (2009) researched on the impact of marketing strategies on profitability of small grocery shops in South African townships. The study sought to ascertain whether grocery shop owners in Mdantsane, East London, adopt marketing strategies that maximizes their profitability. The empirical research component of the study consisted survey using a self-administered questionnaire.

The study found that retailers in Mdantsane use marketing strategies to maximize profit, and regarded price as the most important aspect when applying the marketing strategy mix. This implies that retailers, in Mdantsane, compete primarily based on price, but according to the study findings, the retailers in Mdantsane need to adopt the other 3 Ps of the marketing strategy, namely product, place and packaging in order to be more profitable.

Connecting the relevance of the study by Chiliya, Herbst and Roberts-Lombard (2009), the study was based on marketing strategy which display is also a part of. However, while that study sought how the use of marketing strategy could influence profit, this study is based on the use of advertising display strategy to influence product sales.

Sindhya (2013) in his work studied the impact of advertising to consumer purchase motive among student teachers. The study investigated the impact of advertising on consumer preferences and loyalty with regards to the product/service promotion of different products among student teachers of Kerala. Survey method was used for the study. This was supported by questionnaire and interview tools. The instruments were administered on a sample of 200 student teachers selected from two colleges in rural and urban based.

The study found that advertising has influence on consumer preferences and loyalty of product. The study also found that the level of awareness of the effect of advertisement is comparatively better than expected among the student teachers. Many of them are active listeners of the media for gathering information regarding the new products, trend in the market and make a comparison with the products of other firms. The consumer culture is more prevalent in rural students than in urban students. Majority of female students are interested in cosmetics and jewelry while the male students are more concerned with automobiles and electronic equipment.

The study by Sindhya (2013) is related to this study in that the work centered on advertising influence on consumers' preferences and loyalty of product. This current study however seeks to investigate the impact of advertising window display strategy on product sales by retailers.

2.6 Theoretical Framework

Three theories have been applied in this study. They include; the Persuasion Theory, the AIDA Model of Communication and Source Credibility Theory.

2.6.1 Persuasion Theory

This theory is based on the idea of Aristotle and his rhetorical theory of communication. The basic idea of persuasion has ancient roots long before the age of mass communication the term rhetoric was used to refer to the art of using language to influence the judgments and conducts of others. During the time when human voice was the only medium of communication that could be used in courts of law and in presenting proposal before political forums (Rokeach and Deflaur, 1989).

According to *Higgins and Walker (2012)*, persuasion began with the Greeks, who emphasized rhetoric and elocution as the highest standard for a successful politician. All trials were held in front of the Assembly, and both the prosecution and the defense rested, as they often do today, on the persuasiveness of the speaker. Rhetoric was the ability to find the available means of persuasion in any instance. Corroborating, Wells, Bonnet and Moriarty (1995) assert that persuasion has been around since the dawn of human history. It was formalized as a concept more than 2000 years ago by the Greeks who made (rhetoric), the art of using language effectively and persuasively. Aristotle was the first to set down the idea of ethos, logos, and pathos which was roughly translated as source credibility, logical argument and emotional appeals.

According to Folarin (1998), persuasion is the process whereby an attempt is made to induce change in attitude and behaviour through involvement of persons' cognitive and affective process. He adds that for a persuasive message to be effective, it must succeed in altering the psychological functioning of the recipient in such a way that he or she will respond overtly with models of behaviour desired or suggested by the communicator. Corroborating, Seiter, Robert and Gass (2010) asserts that persuasion is an umbrella term of influence. Persuasion can attempt to influence a person's beliefs, attitudes, intentions, motivations, or behaviours. In business, persuasion is a process aimed at changing a person's (or a group's) attitude or

behaviour toward some event, idea, object, or other person(s), by using written or spoken words to convey information, feelings, or reasoning, or a combination thereof. Persuasion is also an often used tool in the pursuit of personal gain, such as election campaigning, giving a sales pitch, or in trial advocacy. Persuasion can also be interpreted as using one's personal or positional resources to change people's behaviours or attitudes. Systematic persuasion is the process through which attitudes or beliefs are leveraged by appeals to logic and reason (Schacter, Daniel and Daniel, 2011).

To Sandage, Vernon and Kin (1983), persuasion is the process that occurs when a communicator (sender) influences the values, beliefs attitudes, or behaviour of another person (receiver). We can say that it is an activity or process in which communication attempts to induce a change in the belief, value, attitude or behaviour of another person or group of persons through the transmission of a message in a context in which the persuader has some degree of free choice.

The thrust of this theory according to Rokeach and Deflaur (1989) is that persuasion refers primarily to the use of mass media to present messages that are deliberately designed to elicit audiences or complying with requests for action that a communicator wants to elicit. In the same vein, Okechuku (2001) asserts that persuasion seeks to change the belief, thinking, and/or the behaviour of the listener, viewer or reader, with the aid of adequate and factual information provided by properly conducted research. Persuasive message must however be well structured, laden with logical reasoning factors and figures and must be statistically tested and proven so as to produce the desired effect.

Rokeach and Deflaur (1989) posit that, persuasion must focus on either emotional or cognitive factors. They maintained that it is obviously impossible to modify an inherited biological factor (height, weight, race, sex etc.) with mass communication messages. According to them it is possible to use mass communication messages to arouse an emotional state such as anger or fear, which can then be important in shaping responses.

Writing on the basic assumptions of persuasion theory, Fautsch (2007) states that the Greek philosopher Aristotle listed four reasons why one should learn the art of persuasion:

1. Truth and justice are perfect; thus, if a case loses, it is the fault of the speaker
2. It is an excellent tool for teaching
3. A good rhetorician needs to know how to argue both sides to understand the whole problem and all the options, and
4. There is no better way to defend one's self.

Fautsch (2007) maintained further that; Aristotle's rhetorical proofs are centered on:

1. Ethos (credibility)
2. Logos (reason)
3. Pathos (emotion)

The relevance of this anchor theory to this work lies in the fact that the so much desired patronage sought after through advertising can be attained using persuasive communication (the display strategy). By employing persuasion, an attempt is made to influence customers and even passerby to enter a shop and purchase product. Display strategy is therefore a persuasive means of luring customers for retailers' product.

2.6.2 AIDA MODEL

American advertising and sales pioneer, Elias St. Elmo Lewis, is largely credited for developing the AIDA model in one of his publications on advertising in 1898 (Boundless Marketing, 2014). According to Coolson (1947), Lewis developed his discussion of copy principles on the formula that good copy should attract attention, awaken interest, and create conviction. The mission of an advertisement is to sell goods. To do this, it must attract attention, of course; but attracting attention is only an auxiliary detail. The announcement should contain matter which will interest and convince after the attention has been attracted.

According to Boundless Marketing (2014), Lewis identified three principles that should be present in an advertisement:

- The mission of an advertisement is to attract a reader, so that he will look at the advertisement and start to read it.
- The advertisement must then interest him, so that he will continue to read it.
- Finally, the advertisement must convince him, so that when reads it, he will believe it.

Lewis believed that if an advertisement contained these three qualities, then it is an effective advertisement. Wijaya (2012) noted that the AIDA model is an approach used by advertisers to describe the different phases of consumer engagement with an advertisement. AIDA is an acronym used in marketing and advertising that describes a common list of events that may occur when a consumer engages with an advertisement. Elements of the acronym are:

- A: Attention (awareness) - attract the attention of the customer;
- I: Interest of the customer;
- D: Desire – to convince customers that they want and desire the product or service and that it will satisfy their needs;
- A: Action - which leads customers towards taking action and/or purchasing the product.

Joseph (2014) presents an explanation to the components of the model as follows:

Attention:

The attention portion of the marketing message occurs at the beginning and is designed to give the prospects a reason to take notice. Presenting a shocking fact or statistic that identifies a problem which can be solved by the product or service is one common method of gaining attention. Other methods can include asking a thought-provoking question or using the element of surprise. The purpose is to give the prospects a reason for wanting to learn more.

Interest:

Once you have gained the prospects' attention, the next step is to maintain interest in your product or service to keep the recipients engaged. Explain to the recipients how the problem you have identified in the attention step is adversely affecting their lives. A demonstration or illustration can help the recipients to further identify with the problem and want to actively seek possible solutions. By personalizing the problem, you are making it hit closer to home.

Desire:

In the desire stage, your objective is to show the prospects how your product or service can solve their problem. Explain the features of the product or service and the related benefits and demonstrate how the benefits fulfill the need. A common advertising process is the 'before and after' technique, such as when a cleaning product makes a soiled item look brand new. If done effectively, the prospects should now have the desire to make a purchase.

Action:

Now that you have created the desire to make a purchase, the final step is to persuade the prospects to take immediate action. In a one-on-one sales process, this is the time to ask for the sale. In the advertising world, techniques involve creating sense of urgency by extending an offer for a limited time or including a bonus of special gift to those who act within a specific time frame. Without a specific call to action, the prospect may simply forget about your offer and move on.

The AIDA model of advertising is related to this study because it is a practical guide to display strategy of advertising. Thus, by engaging in window display, the retailers are already in the process of drawing attention to the product. As customers and passerby see the displayed product, interest is attained. This may automatically create desire in the minds of customers. Accordingly, when the desire or urge for the product is high, the only thing that can quench the taste is purchase. Display strategy therefore satisfies the demands of AIDA model (Attention, Interest, Desire and Action), thus its relevant to this study.

2.6.3 Source Credibility Theory

In their book 'Communication and Persuasion' the Source Credibility theory was propounded by Hovland, C.I., Janis, I.L., and Kelley, H.H. in 1953. The Source Credibility theory states that people are more likely to be persuaded when the source presents itself as credible. The basic tenet of the theory is that one of the variables in a communication situation over which the communicator typically has some control is the choice of the source. Judging from many day-to-day examples of communication campaigns there appears to be a widespread belief that having the right source can increase the effectiveness of a messages. When you select an effective source to speak for your idea or product, you are essentially using the propaganda device of the testimonial.

The theory is broken into three models that can be used to more aptly apply the theory. The names of those models are: the factor model, the functional model, and the constructivist model. The three models help to narrow the wide scope of the source credibility theory, while also making it a much more focused strategy to use when studying communication. The factor model (a covering laws approach) helps determine to what extent the receiver judges the source as credible. The functional model (a covering laws approach) views credibility as the degree to which a source satisfies a receiver's individual needs. The constructivist model (a human action approach) analyzes what the receiver does with the source's proposal (Griffin, 2000).

Hovland, Janis and Kelley (1953) explaining their theory present the basic premise of the theory as follows:

Ontological Assumptions: The source credibility theory has multiple realities because there are numerous different ways of looking at things from within the theory.

Epistemological Assumptions: Source credibility theory is an approach that allows different individuals to look at things from their own perspective, thus, it is dependent.

Axiological Assumptions: Source credibility theory deals with communication study in a way that is value-laden, and takes into consideration that, different researchers will have their own opinion.

The Source Credibility theory is relevant to this study as it recognizes the effectiveness of high credibility in product retailers displayed. Customers often believe that products displayed are of high value than those not displayed. Hence the importance they attach to the product the shop where they are buying the product. With the level of credibility attach to a particular shop and on product displayed, customers can make many purchase decision within the store. Companies recognize this fact and that is why they encourage the retailers by providing them with beautiful merchandisers to improve shop environment.

2.7 Chapter Summary

This chapter dwells on the review of related literature to the study. Under the review of concepts, the chapter demystified retailer, display strategy and advertising. The review of literature further centered on the relevance of advertising in the society and display adverts on product sales. Four empirical works were reviewed to give an empirical touch to this study. These are studies by Ayanwale, Alimi and Ayanbimipe (2005) on influence of advertising on consumer brand preferences; Kanchori (2014) on influence of digital signage usage on product sales among leading supermarket in Kenya; Chiliya, Herbst and Roberts-Lombard (2009) on impact of marketing strategy on profitability of small grocery shops in South Africa; and the study by Sindhya (2013) on the impact of advertising to customer purchase motives among student teachers.

The theoretical framework is centered on Persuasion theory, AIDA Model of communication and Source Credibility theory. These theories all explained some forms of persuasion, influence or motive why people attend to advertising messages. The literature reviewed however showed that display advertising is capable of inducing patronage for the product or services advertised. Based on this background, this study investigates how display strategy of advertising influence product sales in Makurdi metropolis of Benue State.

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter treats the research method adopted by the researcher in obtaining the necessary data for this study. The chapter is divided into eight segments namely: research design, population of the study, sample size, sampling technique and procedure, research instruments and administration, method of data collection, method of data analysis and validity of instrument.

3.2 Research Design

The survey research method was employed by the researcher as the methodology for collecting data. Research design usually serves as the blue-print which specifies how data relating to a given problem should be collected and analyzed. Thus, Wimmer and Dominic (2000, P.101) maintain that “survey can be used to investigate problems in realistic settings. He adds that the method is also more economical and easier to handle”. Emaikwu (2008) further states that:

Survey method is one in which a group of people is studied by collecting and analyzing data from only a few people considered to be representative of the entire population. It also specifies how data collected will be analyzed.

Thus, survey method avails itself as the data collection design for this study since everyone in the total population cannot be reached in a single study of this nature. Accordingly, the survey method as used in this study employs questionnaire tool as the instruments for collecting data in this study. According to Emaikwu (2008, P. 305), “questionnaires are effective tools for obtaining information about interest, attitudes and opinions. In this study therefore, a list of written questions was drawn and given to responds in to fill.

The choice of using the instrument was to obtain diverse views and opinions on the study objectives. Thus, the survey research design offers the researcher the opportunity to probe obscured areas of the research. It also enables the researcher to gather diverse views and opinions on the topic, “influence of Advertising Window Display Strategy on Product Sales by Retailers in Makurdi Metropolis of Benue State”.

3.3 Population of the Study

This study has a population which comprises all the 10,253 registered shops and supermarkets owners in Makurdi Metropolis of Benue State (Benue State Internal Revenue Services, BIRS, 2013).

3.4 Sample Size Determination

In this study, a sample size of 385 respondents was statistically determined using Taro Yamane’s formula for a finite population in Uzoagulu (1998, p.66). The formula is given as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)}$$

Where:

n= Sample Size

N=the finite population

E=limit of tolerable error (0.05)

I=unity (a constant)

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{10,253}{1 + 10,253(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{10,253}{1 + 10,253 \times 0.0025}$$

$$n = \frac{10.253}{1 + 25.6325}$$

$$n = \frac{10,253}{26.6325}$$

$$n = 384.98 \text{ (That is 385 approximately)}$$

thus, the sample size for the study is 385.

3.5 Sampling Technique and Procedure

To determine the Sampling procedure adopted for this study, the researcher employed both stratified sampling and purposive sampling techniques for this study. Using the stratified sampling method, the researcher used the laid down stratification of Makurdi metropolis into 11 council wards namely:

Agan council ward; Ankpa council ward; Bar council ward; Central/South Mission council ward; Fiidi council ward; Market/Clerk council ward; Mbalagh council ward; and Wailomayo council ward.

Thus, considering the nature of this research which is centered on window displays in shops, supermarket and business premises, only council wards that are typical of these characteristic or shop business populated were selected through the purposive sampling method. Hence, the following council wards were selected because of their characteristics of having much shops, supermarket and business concentrate. The wards selected include: Ankpa council ward; Market/Clerk council ward; Modern Market council ward; North Bank I council ward; Wailomayo council ward; Central South Mission council ward.

By adopting these processes, the researcher arrived at six Council Wards that were used for the study on Influence of Advertising Window Display Strategy on Product Sales by Retailers in Makurdi Metropolis of Benue State. Thus, respondents were drawn from major supermarkets, shops, and markets. The distribution of the 385 respondents among the six selected Council Wards is shown below.

Table. 3.1 Selected Council Wards and Distribution of Respondents

S/N	Council Ward	Selected Number of Respondents
1	Ankpa Council Ward	64
2	Market/Clerk Council Ward	64
3	Modern Market Council Ward	65
4	North Bank I Council Ward	64
5	Wailomayo Council Ward	64
6	Central Mission Council Ward	64
	TOTAL	385

3.6 Research Instruments and Administration

The Advertising Window Display Influence Questionnaire (AWDIQ) was used as the research instrument for this study. The 16-item question AWDIQ was divided into two parts (section A and B). Section A of the AWDIQ elicited demographic information on the respondents, while section B elicited information that are meant to answer the four research questions raised in this study. The questions were designed in both close and open-ended question format to reduce the risk of inconsistencies that may arise from the respondents.

To further determine the procedure for the administration of the study AWDIQ, the researcher, with the help of five research assistants (trained on questionnaire administration)

administered the AWDIQ on the 385 respondents as defined in Table 3.1. Each of the five assistants covered one council ward, while the researcher covered the remaining ward.

3.7 Method of Data Collection

This study used both primary and secondary methods of data collection. The primary data was generated through the Advertising Window Display Influence Questionnaire (AWDIQ) administered on respondents. Secondary data were generated through library materials, books, journal articles and internet.

3.8 Method of Data Analysis

The data collected in this study were analyzed using simple percentages drawn in tables for each of the questions answered in the AWDIQ. The researcher interprets each table using distribution frequencies and explanatory notes for better understanding and conceptualization of the analysis. Also, formulated hypotheses were tested using t-test statistical tool and Chi-square Correlation, to test significant differences and relationships between the study variables.

3.9 Validity and Reliability of Study

Foremost, validity deals with genuineness, faithfulness and authenticity of the instruments used in the study. Reliability on the other hand is concern with consistency and dependability of the study. Thus, data collected through the use of AWDIQ techniques were documented in accurate and unbiased manner. Also, the research instrument used was thoroughly scrutinized by the research supervisor who vetted and monitored the research proceedings.

Also, the researcher conducted a pilot study by pre-testing the questionnaire on 20 persons in the Wadata Market before embarking on the actual field study. This, the researcher did by visiting the randomly administering specimen of AWDIQ to sub-respondents who are not the actual surveyed respondents for this study. The overall mean and variance of the test show 4.247 and 794 respectively (see Appendix II for the details). The result was further subjected to the Cronbach coefficient alpha method and found AWDIQ=943 reliable (see Appendix II for details).

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Introduction

This section deals with the presentation, analysis, and discussion of findings generated through the administration of the study questionnaire. The data were presented in tables and analyzed using simple percentages to make inferences on the four research questions raised in this study. Also, the hypotheses were tested using a t-test statistical tool and Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient. The presentation and analysis of results is however based on the 384 (out of 385) copies of AWDIQ that were retrieved from the field.

4.2.1 Data Presentation

Foremost, the bio-data or demographic information of respondents obtained from the field survey will be presented, and thereafter the data which sought to meet the objectives of this study will be presented and analyzed.

Table 1: Sex of Respondents

Sex	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Male	178	46%
Female	206	54%
Total	384	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2015

In table 1, the sex distribution of respondents was sought. Thus, the table revealed that there are 178 male respondents (46%) the responded to the Advertising Window Display Influence Questionnaire (AWDIQ). Also, female respondents comprised 206 respondents representing 54% of the study population. This result even though implies that the female respondents are more than the male shows that both sexes own shops and supermarkets in Makurdi metropolis.

Table 1: Age of Respondents

Age Bracket	No. of Respondents	Percentage
18-30 years	67	17.4%
31-40 years	185	48.1%
41-50 years	100	26.0%
51- years & above	32	8.3%
Total	384	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2015

The data in table 2 indicates the age range of respondents. Thus, 67 respondents (17.4%) were within the ages of 18-30 years, 185 respondents (48.1%) were within 31-40 years. Also, 100 respondents (26.0%) were between 41-50 years, while 32 respondents (8.3%) were between 51 years and above. The result shows that the respondents cut across different age grade and could state their reasons for advertising window display in their various shops.

Table 3: Occupational Distribution of Respondents

Occupation	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Trader	125	32%
Businessman/woman	100	26%
Shop Attendant	68	18%
Chief Executive Officer	91	24%
Total	384	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2015

The data gathered and presented in Table 3 shows that 125 respondents (32%) are traders, 100 respondents (26%) are businessmen/women. Also, 68 respondents (18%) are shop attendants, while the remaining 91 respondents representing 24% are Chief Executive Officers of their businesses. This also implies that the study on influence of advertising window display strategy covers various categories of the business people.

Table 4: Educational Qualification of Respondents

Educational status	No. of Respondents	Percentage
First School Leaving Certificate	43	11%
SSCE/Grade II	162	42%
OND/ND/NCE	127	33%
Degree/Master/PhD	52	14%
Total	384	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2015

Table 4 shows the educational qualification of respondents. Thus, among those who filled the questionnaire, 43 respondents (11%) have First School Leaving Certificate, 162 respondents (42%) have SSCE/Grade II certificates; 127 respondents (33%) have OND/ND/NCE certificates; 52 respondents (14%) have their First Degrees, Master and Ph.D.

The result in table shows that, the respondents are enlightened enough to serve the purpose of this study.

Table 5: Business Location of Respondents according to Council Ward

Location	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Ankpa Council Ward	64	16.6%
Market/Clerk Council Ward	64	16.6%
Modern Market Council Ward	65	16.9%
North Bank I Council Ward	64	16.6%
Wailomayo Council Ward	63	16.4%
Central Mission Council Ward	64	16.6%
Total	384	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2015

Table 5 shows the distribution of respondents in accordance to their various locations in Makurdi metropolis. Thus, a total of 64 respondents representing 16.6% of the respondents are from Ankpa, Market/Clerk, North Bank I and Central Mission wards respectively. Modern Market ward had 65 respondents (16.8%) and Wailomayo had 63 respondents (16.4%) respectively. The implication of this result is that the respondents cut across various locations within Makurdi metropolis.

Table 6: Respondents' Awareness of Advertising Window Display Strategy

Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	384	100%
No	-	-
Total	384	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2015

Table 6 sought whether the respondents are aware of advertising window display strategy. Thus, the entire 384 respondents representing 100% attested to the fact that they are aware of advertising window display strategy. This therefore implies that there is business awareness of advertising window display strategy in Makurdi Metropolis.

Table 7: The Use of Advertising Window Display Strategy

Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Very often	196	51%
Often	127	33%
Seldom	61	16%
Not at all	-	-
Total	384	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2015

Table 7 determines how often respondents use advertising window display strategy in their various business shops or supermarket. The responses indicate that, 196 respondents (51%) use advertising window display strategy very often, 127 respondents (33%) adopt the strategy often and the remaining 67 respondents (16%) use advertising window display strategy occasionally. This therefore implies that business people use advertising window display strategy.

Table 8: How Advertising Window Display Induce Sales of Products

Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Very often	196	51%
Often	127	33%
Seldom	61	16%
Not at all	-	-
Total	384	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2015

Table 8 determines how often respondents use advertising windows display strategy induce product sales in shops or supermarkets. Thus, 196 respondents (51%) affirmed that the use advertising window display strategy induce produce sales very often, 127 respondents (33%) affirmed that it induce sales often. The remaining 67 respondents (16%) attested that the use advertising window display strategy influence sales of product occasionally. This implication of this result is that advertising window display influences the sales of products.

Table 9: Extent to which Advertising Window Display Influences Sales of Products

Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
High	79	21%
Average	269	70%
Low	36	9%
Poor	-	-
Total	384	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2015

Table data in Table 9 show the extent to which advertising window display influences sales of product. Thus, a total of 79 respondents (21%) attested to a high sales rate as a result of advertising window display strategy. Also, an overwhelming 269 respondents (70%) attested to average sales rate as a result of advertising window display strategy. The remaining 36 respondents (9%) attested to low sales rate as a result of advertising window display strategy. This therefore implies that advertising window display strategy influences product sales, however, the extent of influence is what will be tested in the hypotheses.

Table 10: Rating Advertising Window Display Strategy in terms of Sales Generated

Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Excellent (90-100%)	122	32%
High (70-80%)	1283	48%
Average (50-60%)	79	20%
Low (30-40%)	-	-
Very low (10-20%)	-	-
Total	384	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2015

Table 10 sought the rating of advertising window display in terms of sales generated. Thus, 122 respondents (32%) attested that the extent is excellent (i.e. between 90-100%). An overwhelming 48% of the study (i.e. 183 respondents) maintained that the extent is high (i.e. 90-80%). The remaining 79 respondents (20%) however said that the extent is average.

Table 11: How Use of Display Strategy Influences Product Sales

Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
By making the customer to look twice	30	8%
Luring the customer into the shop	41	11%
Giving the customer the opportunity to see all the shop stock	84	22%
Making the customer to purchase products from the shop	177	46%
All of the above		
Total	384	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2015

Responses sought in Table 11 sought how the use of advertising display strategy influences product sales. Accordingly, the 30 respondents (8%) said by making the customer to look twice, 41 respondents (11%) said by luring the customer into the shop. Another 84 respondents representing 22% of the study population said by giving the customer the opportunity to see all the shop stock. While 52 respondents (13%) attested to by making the customer to purchase product from the shop, overwhelming 177 respondents (46%) attested to all of the above option. This means that all the options are captured in their responses.

Table 12: Rating the Influence Nature of Advertising Window Display Strategy on Product Sales

Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Highly favourable	238	62%
Favourable	146	38%
Unfavourable	-	-
Grossly unfavourable	-	-
Total	384	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2015

The data in table 12 shows the influence nature of advertising window display strategy on product sales. A total of 238 respondents (62%) said the influence is highly favourable. The remaining 146 respondents (38%) said it was favourable. This result implies that the influence nature of advertising window display strategy on product sales some positive level of favourability.

Table 13: The Nature of Relationship between Advertising Display Strategy and Product Sales by Retailers

Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Very positive	238	62%
Positive	146	38%
Negative	-	-
Grossly Negative	-	-
Total	384	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2015

The data in Table 13 sought the nature of relationship between advertising display strategy and product sales by retailers. A total 238 respondents (62%) attested to the fact that

the nature of relationship is very positive. The remaining 146 respondents representing 38% of the study sample maintained that the nature of relationship is positive. These contending views are however subject to further test.

Table 14: Advocate for the Continuous use of Advertising Window Display Strategy

Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Very well	384	100%
Not quite	-	-
Not at all	-	-
Can't say	-	-
Total	384	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2015

Table 14 sought whether there is an advocacy for the continuous use of advertising window display strategy. The 384 respondents (i.e. 100%) advocated for the continuous use of advertising window display strategy. This result however implies that advertising window display strategy has good influence on product sales by retailers.

Table 15: Nature of the Relationship between Advertising Display Strategy and Product Sales by Retailers

Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Smooth	99	26%
Cordial	285	74%
Uneven	-	-
Unpleasant	-	-
Total	384	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2015

The data in Table 15 shows the nature of the relationship between advertising display strategy and product sales by retailers. A total 99 respondents (26%) attested to the fact that the nature of relationship is a smooth one. The remaining overwhelming 285 respondents (74%) attested to the fact that the nature of relationship is cordial. This therefore means that advertising display strategy has smooth and cordial relationship on product sales.

Table 16: Recommendation on Improving Advertising Display Strategy

Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Helping customers find locations within the store	67	17%
Enhance the store ambiance and Environment	152	40%
Improve marketing and merchandising Effectiveness	44	11%
Increase operational efficiency	-	-
Improve corporate communications and training	-	-
Promote new products, product lines, or product categories	121	32%
Total	384	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2015

The data in Table 16 sought ways through which advertising window display strategy could be improved upon. Thus, 67 respondents recommended helping customers find locations within the store, 152 respondents (40%) recommended enhancing the store ambiance and environment. Also, 44 respondents (11%) recommended Improving marketing and merchandising effectiveness and the remaining 121 respondents recommended promoting new products, products lines, or product categories.

4.2.2 Answering Research Questions

This section seeks to analyze the questionnaire data presented in section 4.2.1 in the manner in which the research questions were answered. In this study, the four research questions raised were answered in the following order:

Research Question One

To what extent are retailers aware of advertising display strategy and use it to induce product sales in Benue State?

To answer the first research question, tables 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 provided the direction into which it was answered. Table 6 first of all determines whether the public are aware of advertising display strategy. The study discovered that the retailers are aware. This position was affirmed by the entire 384 respondents, representing 100% of the study respondents.

Data in Table 7 determines how often respondents use advertising window display strategy in their various business shops or supermarket. The responses indicate that, 196 respondents (51%) use advertising window display strategy very often, 127 respondents (33%) adopt the strategy often and the remaining 67 respondents (16%) use advertising window display strategy occasionally.

Furthermore, Table 8 determines how often respondents use advertising window display strategy induce product sales in shops or supermarket. Thus, 196 respondents (51%) affirmed that the use of advertising window display strategy induce product sales very often, 127 respondents (33%) affirmed that it induce sales often. The remaining 67 respondents (16%) attested that the use advertising window display strategy influence sales of product occasionally.

The data in Table 9 showed the extent to which advertising window display influences sales of product. Thus, a total of 79 respondents (21%) attested to a high sales rate as a result of advertising window display strategy. Also, an overwhelming 269 respondents (70%) attested to average sales rate as a result to advertising window display strategy. The remaining 36 respondents (9%) attested to low sales rate as a result of advertising window display strategy.

Table 10 sought the rating of advertising window display in terms of sales generated. Thus, 122 respondents (32%) attested that the extent is excellent (i.e. between 90-100%). An overwhelming 48% of the study (i.e. 183 respondents) maintained that the extent is high (i.e. 70-80%). The remaining 79 respondents (20%) however said that the extent is average. Hence, with the information in tables 6-10, the demands of research question one which sought the extent to which retailers are aware of advertising display strategy are met.

Research Question Two

How has retailers use display strategy of advertising to influence product sales in Benue State?

To answer the second research question raised in this study, tables 11 and 12 shed light on the demands of the second research question. Thus, Table 11 sought how the use of advertising display strategy influences product sales. Accordingly, the 30 respondents (8%) said by making the customer to look twice, 41 respondents (11%) said by luring the customer into the shop. Another 84 respondents representing 22% of the study population said by giving the customer the opportunity to see all the shop stock. While 52 respondents (13%) attested to by making the customer to purchase product from the shop, overwhelming 177 respondents (46%) attested to all of the above option. This means that all the options are captured in their responses.

Lastly on the second research question, table 12 shows the influence nature of advertising window display strategy on product sales. A total of 238 respondents (62%) said the influence is highly favourable. The remaining 146 respondents (38%) said it was favourable. This result implies that the influence nature of advertising window display strategy on product sales some positive level of favourability.

Research Question Three

What is the nature of relationship between advertising display strategy and product sales by retailers in Benue State?

To answer this research question, tables 13, 14 and 15, 16 shed light on the demands of this research question. First of all, the data in Table 13 sought the nature of relationship between advertising display strategy and product sales by retailers. A total of 238 respondents (62%) attested to the fact the nature of relationship is very positive. The remaining 146 respondents representing 38% of the study sample maintained that the nature of relationship is positive.

Furthermore, responses in Table 14 sought whether there is an advocacy for the continuous use of advertising window display strategy. The 384 respondents (i.e. 100%) advocated for the continuous use of advertising window display strategy. The data in Table 15 show the nature of the relationship between advertising display strategy and product sales by retailers. A total of 99 respondents (26%) attested to the fact that the nature of relationship is a smooth one. The remaining overwhelming 285 respondents (74%) attested to the fact that the nature of relationship is cordial. This therefore means that advertising display strategy has smooth and cordial relationship on product sales. With this provisions however, the demand of research question three which sought the nature of relationship between advertising display strategy and product sales by retailers in Benue State was answered.

Research Question Four

What possible recommendations could be made for the improvement of advertising display strategy by retailers in Benue State?

The fourth research question raised in this study was answered using responses in table 16. The data in Table 16 sought ways through which advertising window display strategy could be improved upon. Thus, 67 respondents recommended helping customers find locations within the store, 152 respondents (40%) recommended enhancing the store ambiance and environment. Also, 44 respondents (11%) recommended improving marketing

and merchandising effectiveness and the remaining 121 respondents recommended promoting new products, product lines, or product categories.

4.3 Test of Hypotheses

This section verifies the two null hypotheses formulated in chapter one of this study. The hypotheses are thereby put forward for testing thus:

Hypothesis One;

H_{01} : *There is no significant relationship in the use of display strategy by retailers and product sales in Benue State.*

H_1 . *There is significant relationship in the use of display strategy by retailers and product sales in Benue State.*

Using data in tables 13 and 15, the first formulated hypothesis was tested using Chi-Square. This tool was used to ascertain the significant level of relationship between the use of display strategy by retailers and product sales in Makurdi metropolis of Benue State. The result is presented as follows:

X^2_{cal}	$X^2_{Crit.}$	Sig. Level	Remark
102.36	15.507	8	Significant

Thus, the Chi-square correlation (X^2) was found to be 102.36 and the critical value at 0.05 level of significance was 15.507 (hence, $X^2_{cal.} 102.36 > X^2_{tab.} 15.507$; see Appendix III for detailed calculations). This means that, there is significant positive relationship in the use of display strategy by retailers and product sales in Benue State. Base on the decision rule to reject H_0 if X^2 calculated is greater than X^2 tabulated, thus, the null hypothesis which states that, “there is no significant positive relationship in the use of display strategy by retailers and product sales in Benue State” is rejected and the alternate accepted.

Hypothesis Two:

H_{02} : *There is no significant relationship in the use of advertising display strategy and product sales by retailers in Benue State.*

H_2 . *There is significant relationship in the use of advertising display strategy and product sales by retailers in Benue State.*

Using data in tables 9, and 10, the second formulated hypothesis was tested using t-test. This tool was used to ascertain the level of significant difference between advertising display strategy influence and product sales by retailers in Benue State. The result shows that:

Variables	N	ND	t-cal	t-tab	Remark
Advertising Window Display Influence on Product Sales	384				
Rating Advertising Window Display Strategy in terms of Sales Generated	384	383	2.136	1.96	Significant

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

The t-test result shows that the investigation is significant. The t_{cal} was found to be 2.136 while the t-critical was found to be 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance (see appendix III for detailed calculations). Thus, based on the decision rule to reject H_0 if the calculated value is greater than the tabulated value, the null hypothesis which state that, “there is no significant difference between advertising display strategy influence and product sales by retailers in Benue State” is rejected and the alternate accepted. With the rejection of the null hypothesis, it implies that there is significant influence in using advertising display strategy on product sales by retailers in Benue State.

4.5 Discussion of Finding

This section correlates the findings generated in this study. The section relates the findings of the questionnaire administered on the field with the theoretical framework and review of literature made in this study. The section is treated chronologically in the order of the research questions and hypotheses raised in this work.

Foremost, the study finds out that retailers are aware of display strategy and use advertising window display strategy very often in Benue State. Also, to determine how often respondents use advertising window display strategy induce product sales in shops or supermarket. The study found that the use advertising window display strategy induce product sales very often. The study however found that there is a high and average sales rate as a result of advertising window display strategy in designated shops.

Thus, owing to the fact that display strategy influence product sales by retailer, this validate the essence of the three theories used in this study. Persuasion theory which is the anchor theory for this study is based on the premise that persuasion influence a person’s beliefs, attitudes, intentions, motivations, or behaviours. In business, persuasion as a process aimed at changing a person’s (or a group’s) attitude or behavior toward products or services. This also agrees with the AIDA model used in the study. By engaging in window display, the retailers are already in the process of drawing attention to the product. As customers and passerby see the displayed product, interest is attained. This may automatically create desire in the minds of customers. Accordingly, when the desire or urge for the product is high, the only thing that can quench the taste is purchase. Display strategy therefore satisfies the demands of AIDA model. The Source Credibility Theory used in the study is also validated. This is because customers often believe those products displayed are of high value than those not displayed (in most case). Hence, they attach importance to the product displayed and even the shop where they are buying the product since there is high sense of credibility.

The finding also agrees with Hiam and Charls (1992) who pointed out that advertising strategies focus on achieving three general goals of;

1. Promoting awareness of a business and its product or services;
2. Stimulating sales directly and attract competitors’ customers; and
3. Establishing or modifying a business’ image

The study also found the there is significant positive relationship in the use of display strategy by retailers and product sales. This correlation simply means display are very impactful to shop business. This is because the essence of operating the shop or supermarket is to generate sale and make profit. This is one of the key reasons why Hendel and Nevo (2006) stated that the main objectives of display strategy of adverting whether traditional or modern is to enhance sales. This was also corroborated by Horvitz (1998) who maintained that a renewed faith among retailers in the ability of window displays is to capture consumers’ attention and draw them into a store. This paucity is underscored by the possibility that window displays, in their effect on retailer-related cognitions and decisions,

can function both as advertising and sales promotion. Park, Jaworski and Macinnis (1986) also echo this fact where they said that window displays are akin to advertising in helping create and maintain an overall image of the retailer in consumers' minds.

The study further found that there is a very positive relationship between advertising display strategy and product sale. Hence, tested hypothesis revealed that there is significant influence in using advertising display strategy on product sales by retailers in Benue State. This means that display strategy and retailers are not at variance or disarray with one another. In fact, Kaufman (1987) earlier mentioned that displays at the point of purchase (POP) are a widely used as retailing device for drawing customer's attention. Dwyer and Tanner (2002) affirmed that buyers depend on displays to see new products and keep abreast of the latest information. This, however make display important to business marketers.

5.0 SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of Findings

This study centered on the impact of advertising window display strategy on product sales by retailers in Makurdi metropolis of Benue State. The study thus focused on the nature of relationship and influence of displays on product sales. The survey research method was further adopted as the blue print for eliciting information from the respondents. Accordingly, Advertising Window Display Influence Questionnaire (AWDIQ) was used as data collection tools. The sampled population of the study was drawn from six council wards (out of 11) in Makurdi metropolis. A total of 384 respondents were statistically determined using the Taro Yamane's formula for finite population.

Thus, in resolving the issue of what extent retailers are aware of advertising display strategy and use it to induce product sales in Benue State, the study found that retailers are very much aware of advertising of advertising display strategy. Also, retailers use advertising window display strategy very often to induce product sales. The study however found that there is an average sales rate as a result of advertising window display strategy.

On how retailers use display strategy of advertising to influence product sales in Benue State, the study found that; by making the customer to look twice, by luring the customer into the shop, by giving the customer the opportunity to see all the shop stock and by making the customer to purchase product from the shop. The study also found that the influence nature of advertising window display strategy on product sale is highly favourable. Tests hypothesis also show that there was significant influence in the use of advertising display strategy and product sales by retailers in Benue State.

The third phase of the study sought the nature of relationship between advertising display strategy and product sales by retailers in Benue State. The study found that the nature of relationship is very positive. Tested hypothesis also showed that there was significant positive relationship in the use of display strategy by retailers and product sales in Benue State.

The last phase of the study sought possibly way that could help improve advertising display strategy by retailers in Benue State. The study found that display could be improved upon by; helping customers find locations within the store, enhancing the store ambiance and environment, improving marketing and merchandising effectiveness and by promoting new products, product lines, or product categories.

5.2 Conclusion

This study has established that displays have significant positive influence on retailers' shopping business and that the nature of relationship between displays and product sales by retailers is a very positive one. Based on the data collected and analyzed, this study therefore concludes that, displays are veritable and indispensable marketing tool for shop business. Hence, there are central in fulfilling the persuasive obligation of wooing customers' patronage for a business.

Display strategy is therefore an effective medium of advertising products at the shops or point of purchase and is recommended for shops and supermarket business. Since customers are enticed with the physical appearance of display, there is need to position them strategically as to guide and coordinate shoppers' product selection.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the data generated and analyzed in this study, the following recommendations have been made:

1. Advertising window display being a key marketing communications tool at shopping centers, should be strengthened and never be neglected by retailers who would want to achieve basic objectives of their business.
2. Since retailers are focused on offering a better service to their customers, there is need for proper positioning of products display strategically as to guide and coordinate shoppers' product selection. Whereas, through display customers can also know the worth of what a shop has to offer.
3. The essence of window display is to create awareness and get attention of customers. It is therefore very pertinent that retailers work on improving shop ambient and environment. Beautifying shopping centers with decorative (like lighting, painting, flowers etc.) will add aesthetic to displayed product. This will further achieve its goal of making the customers to want to have a stop-over at the shop.
4. In addition to window display, there is also need for retailers to introduce a mix of other marketing tools. A combination of display with advertising, sales promotion will attract more sales for the business.

5.4 Suggestions for Further Reading

This study even though valid, cannot be said to be complete in all aspect as the study is only limited to retailers in Makurdi metropolis of Benue State. The study is also centered primarily on window display of advertising without investigating other marketing tools. Thus, further studies could be carried out to broaden the scope and introduce more variables that will help improve business conditions of retailers. Also, a broader population and/or respondents could be used to be able to make valid generalizations which could extend beyond the shore of Makurdi metropolis.

Further research on numerous fronts can also help enhance the validity and generalizability of this conclusion. This is because of the limitation that stems from the relatively homogeneous sample population used to test predictions regarding consumers' window display-related decisions. Thus, while the sample population is undoubtedly important to retailers generally, individual product could be isolated and examined as to whether these findings generalize to other relevant populations is an important next step.

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APPENDIX I (A)

LETTER OF INTRODUCTION

Department of Mass Communication,
Benue State University,
P.M.B 102119, Makurdi
Benue State.

Dear Respondent,

I humbly write to solicit your aid as you provide me with the necessary information which will enable me make valid inference in my Master Degree dissertation. I am currently carrying out a study on the topic "Influence of Advertising Window Display on Product Sales by Retailers in Makurdi Metropolis of Benue State".

Please, kindly fill the attached questionnaire to help me collate the necessary data for this study. Your response shall be treated as confidential and shall used for academic and development purpose.

Thanks for your anticipated cooperation.

Yours Faithfully,

Aondo, Jonathan Aernan
BSU/SS/M.Sc/08/4282

APPENDIX I (B)

ADVERTISING WINDOW DISPLAY INFUENCE QUESTIONNAIRE

INFLUENCE OF ADVERTISING WINDOW DISPLAY ON PRODUCT SALES BY RETAILERS IN MAKURDI METROPOLIS OF BENUE STATE.

Instruction: please kindly tick (✓) or provide appropriate answer where necessary. Only one answer should be provided for each of the questions in close-ended format.

Section A: Demographic Data

1. Sex:
 - (a) Male ()
 - (b) Female ()
2. Age:
 - (a) 18 – 30 ()
 - (b) 31 – 40 ()
 - (c) 41 -50 ()
 - (d) 51 and above. ()
3. Occupation/Rank:
 - (a) Trader ()
 - (b) Businessman/Business woman ()
 - (c) Shop Attendant ()
 - (d) Chief Executive Officer ()
4. Educational Qualification:

- (a) First School Leaving Certificate ()
- (b) SSCE/Grade II ()
- (c) OND/ND/NCE ()
- (d) Degree/Master/Ph. D ()

5. Business Location of Respondents according to council ward:

Section B: Research Objective

- 6. Are you aware of advertising window display strategy?
 - (a) Yes ()
 - (b) No ()
- 7. How often do you use advertising window display strategy?
 - (a) Very often ()
 - (b) Often ()
 - (c) Seldom ()
 - (d) Not at all ()
- 8. How often does advertising window display induce sales of products in your shop?
 - (a) Very often
 - (b) Often
 - (c) Occasionally
 - (d) Not at all
- 9. To what extent does advertising window display influence sales of products in your shop?
 - (a) High
 - (b) Average
 - (c) Low
 - (d) Poor
- 10. How would you rate the level of advertising window display in terms of sales generated?
 - (a) Excellent (90-100%) ()
 - (b) High (70-80%) ()
 - (c) Average (50-60%) ()
 - (d) Low (30-40%) ()
 - (e) Very low (10-20%) ()
- 11. How has the use of display strategy of advertising influences product sales among retailers?
 - (a) By making the customers to look twice ()
 - (b) Luring the customer into the shop ()
 - (c) Giving the customer the opportunity to see all the stock ()
 - (d) Making the customer to purchase products from the shop ()
 - (e) All of the above ()
- 12. How will you rate the influence of nature of advertising window display strategy on product sales?
 - (a) Highly favourable ()

- (b) Favourable ()
(c) Unfavourable ()
(d) Grossly unfavourable ()
13. What is the nature of relationship between advertising display strategy and product sales by retailers?
(a) Very positive ()
(b) Positive ()
(c) Negative ()
(d) Grossly negative ()
14. Are you advocating the continuous use of advertising window display strategy to promote retailing?
(a) Very well ()
(b) Not quite ()
(c) Not at all ()
(d) Can't say ()
15. What will you say about the nature of the relationship between advertising display strategy and product sales by retailers?
(a) Smooth ()
(b) Cordial ()
(c) Uneven ()
(d) Unpleasant ()
16. What will you recommend to further improve advertising display strategy among retailers?
(a) Helping customers find locations within the store ()
(b) Enhance the ambience and environment ()
(c) Improve marketing and merchandising effectiveness ()
(d) Increase operational efficiency ()
(e) Improve corporate communications and training ()
(f) Promote new products, product lines, or product categories ()

APPENDIX II

RELIABILITY CALCULATION OF AWDIQ

Reliability calculation of Advertising Window Display Influence Questionnaire (AWDIQ) using Cronbach Alpha method (on SPSS)

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	20	100.0
	Excluded	0	.0
	Total	20	100.0

- a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.947	.943	16

Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
VAR00001	4.7500	.71635	20
VAR00002	4.3500	.74516	20
VAR00003	1.7000	.47016	20
VAR00004	4.5500	.94451	20
VAR00005	4.6500	.81273	20
VAR00006	4.6500	.74516	20
VAR00007	4.6000	.82078	20
VAR00008	4.6500	.81273	20
VAR00009	4.6000	.82078	20
VAR00010	4.7000	.57124	20
VAR00011	2.4000	.82078	20
VAR00012	4.0500	.82558	20
VAR00013	4.7500	.71635	20
VAR00014	4.7000	.92338	20
VAR00015	4.5500	1.05006	20
VAR00016	4.3500	.74516	20

Summary Item Statistics

	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Range	Maximum/Minimum	Variance	N of Items
Item Means	4.247	1.300	4.750	3.450	3.654	.794	16

Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
VAR00001	122.6500	237.608	.873	.	.954
VAR00002	123.0500	240.155	.723	.	.955
VAR00003	125.7000	259.168	-.131	.	.960
VAR00004	122.8500	237.608	.649	.	.956
VAR00005	122.7500	238.618	.722	.	.955
VAR00006	122.7500	237.250	.854	.	.954
VAR00007	122.8000	238.589	.716	.	.955
VAR00008	122.7500	237.882	.753	.	.955
VAR00009	122.8000	238.905	.703	.	.955
VAR00010	122.7000	252.958	.227	.	.958
VAR00011	125.0000	254.632	.080	.	.960
VAR00012	123.3500	243.503	.513	.	.957
VAR00013	122.6500	237.713	.868	.	.954
VAR00014	122.7000	230.958	.912	.	.953
VAR00015	122.8500	231.292	.783	.	.955
VAR00016	122.8500	237.608	.649	.	.956

Scale Statistics

Mean	Variance	Std. Deviation	N of Items
127.4000	257.411	16.04402	16